

Efficacy of Katibasti in the management of Katishoola: A case study

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Abstract

Katishoola is a very common complaint, which is localized Vatavyadhi where Vata dosha affects Katisandhi. In modern it is nearly correlated with Lumbar spondylosis. Katishoola is a disease which is mainly caused by the vitiation of *Vata Dosh*. In Ayurveda Katishoola comes under Vatavyadhi. Management for this is Katibasti as mentioned in the Ayurvedic Texts. Katibasti is one of the popular Panchakarma therapy described as Bahi Parimarjana Chikitsa (external procedure) in Ayurveda. Here in this case we are discussing a successfully treated simple katishoola in a 48-year-old female patient with saharadi taila katibasti.

Keywords: Katishoola; Katibasti; Ayurveda; Sahacharadi taila; Spondylosis

1. Introduction

Katishoola is a condition where the lower back region is afflicted with vitiated Vata and present with symptoms such as pain with stiffness. Katishoola mentioned in ayurveda can be correlated with Lumbar spondylosis due to similarity of clinical manifestations. Katishoola is a disease which is mainly caused by vitiation of Vata Dosh. It has been categorized under Vatika Nanatmaja Vyadhi in Charaka Samhita as Prishta Graha. Katishoola is Shosha, Stambha and Shoola predominant Vyadhi. As correctly said by Sushruta Acharya without vitiation of Vata, Shoola cannot be produced. Katibasti is an Ayurvedic treatment approach of bahyasnehana and swedana

2. Aims and Objectives

To prove the efficacy of katibasti in katishoola chikitsa

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Case Report

- **Presenting Complaints:** A 48-year-old female who is a house wife with 2 children without any comorbidities came to the panchakarma OPD of Dhanvantari Ayurveda Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Siddapur, Karnataka, with complaints of backpain since 1 month
- **Associated Complaints:** Pain and stiffness while sitting and standing along with disturbed sleep since 1 month
- **History of presenting illness:** Patient was apparently normal, since 2 months she started getting back pain along with stiffness gradually leading to disturbed sleep. She consulted a allopathic clinic nearby and was prescribed with NSAIDS and symptoms were relieved which again reoccurred after 1 week. Hence she came to our hospital for better treatment.

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3.1.1. Personal History

- Diet: Vegetarian
- Appetite: Good
- Bowel Habit: Constipated, passes hard stools on alternative days
- Micturition: 1-2 times a day, no burning micturition
- Sleep Pattern: Disturbed 5-6 hours of sleep at night, no day sleep
- Food Habits: Eats oily,spicy, fried foods, and dairy products regularly

3.2. Clinical Examination

3.2.1. General Examination

- General Appearance: Fair
- Built: Medium
- Nourishment: Poorly nourished
- Pallor: Absent
- Lymphadenopathy: Absent
- Odema: Absent

3.3. Vitals

- Blood Pressure: 120/80 mm of Hg
- Pulse Rate: 80b/m
- Temperature: 97.6 degrees Fahrenheit
- SPO2: 98%
- Weight: 62 kg
- Height: 153cm

3.4. Ashtasthana Pareeksha

- Nadi: 80 b/m
- Mutra: 1-2 times/day
- Mala: Constipated, passes hard stools on alternate days
- Jihwa: Aliptha
- Shabdha: Prakruta
- Sparsha: Ruksha
- Druk: Prakruta
- Akruthi: Sthoola

3.5. Dashavidha Pareeksha

- Prakruti: Vata-Pittaja
- Vikruti: Kapha pradhana tridoshaja
- Sara: Madhyama sara
- Samhanana: Asamhata
- Pramana: Madhyama
- Satmya: Madhura pradhana shadrasa
- Satva: Avara satva
- Ahara Shakti; Madyama
- Abhayavaharana Shakti: Madhyama
- Jarana Shakti: Madhyama
- Vyayama Shakti: Madhyama
- Vaya: Madhyama

3.6. Systemic Examination

- **Respiratory System:** NVBS heard, no added sounds
- **Cardio Vascular System:** S1 and S2 heard, no cardiac murmurs
- **Central Nervous System:** Conscious and well-oriented
- **Gastrointestinal System:** P/A - Soft and non-tender, no organomegaly

- **Muskuloskeletal system:** Gait and posture is normal on inspection slight tenderness of muscles and stiffness is present. SLR test is negative.

3.7. Treatment Protocol

Treatment started with koshtashuddi, sadyavirechana given with trivrut lehya 50 gms on day 1, 7 vegas observed. Later on, patient is advised to take liquid food and warm water. After 2 days advised for followup.

3.8. Kati Basti

Kati Basti is a procedure in which retaining of warm Sahacharadi taila with in a specially formed frame in the lumbo-sacral region. It performs the combined action of Snehana and Swedana.

3.9. Purva Karma Preparation of the patient

- The Prakruti and Vikriti of the patient are documented in detail. The disease related examinations are also performed.
- Patient is given a Sadhyo-Virechana for detoxification. This will evacuate the bowel and reduce the pressure over the back and thus enhance the effect of Kati Basti treatment.
- Sambhara Sangraha - Materials needed for the treatment are collected. Make thick dough with black gram powder by mixing with adequate quantity of water.

3.10. Pradhana Karma

Using the thick dough make a rim and fix it firmly on the low back (lumbo-sacral) region where the highest pain is present. Take Sahacharadi taila, warm it and pour on the inner wall of rim taking care not to spill out. When oil becomes cool, remove it with cotton & again refill with warm oil. Uniform temperature should be maintained throughout the procedure. Time and duration of the procedure varies according to the disease condition. Usually, Kati Basti is done for 30-45 minutes for 7 days. Observation of Samyak Yoga Lakshana - Like Sheetagnata, Shoolagnata, Sthambhagnata, Gauravagnata, Mardavata, Svedakarakata.

- Later remove the rim and clean the area with cotton.

4. Observation and results

Table 1 Symptoms Before Treatment & After Treatment

Symptoms	BF	AT
Pain	Grade 3	Grade 1
Stiffness	Grade3	Grade0
Tenderness	Grade3	Grade0
Degree of anterior flexion	45	90

Indications of Kati Basti - Lumbar spondylosis, disc prolapse

5. Discussion

Katishoola simply means pain in low back area. It is a condition due to deranged Vata Dosha. Management included Vatahara procedures described in Ayurveda like Abhyanga, Kativasti, Kshira Vasti, Virechana,

As per Ayurveda, Shoola (pain) occurs due to vitiation of Vata Dosha. Vata Dosha is vitiated by Srotorodha (obstructions of channels) and Dhathu Kshaya (depletion of tissues). In Kati Shoola, Apana Vata (Vata located in the low back region) is mainly involved. So, the aim of the treatment is to pacify vitiated Vata Dosha, especially Apana Vata.

Panchakarma interventions started with Katibasti for 7 days. Katibasti is a Snehayukta Sweda Basti procedure which helps to decrease low back ache, alleviates numbness due to nerve compression & strengthens back muscles which maintain normal curvature of the spine and the bone tissues.

6. Conclusion

It is concluded that this treatment regimen completely relieves the symptoms in Kati Shoola (lumbar spondylosis). These medicines can be utilized in treating patients who are suffering from Kati Shoola, to reduce both signs and symptoms successfully and with greater effectiveness. It is proposed that this therapy can be accepted as a treatment method for Kati Shoola (lumbar spondylosis).

Sahacharadi Tailam is a gingelly oil-based preparation mentioned in the 'Sahasrayoga – Tailaprakarana'. Sahacharadi tailam is indicated for both internal and external application. It is found to have specific efficacy in restoring mobility and function in the lower extremities. It is a simple combination of Vata-hara drugs in a nourishing and warming Sesame oil base.

Sahachara is *Strobilanthes ciliatus*, also known as Kurinji. It is used to treat disorders related to Vata dosha. It is used to prepare medicines to treat low back pain. It can relieve stiffness in the joints of the hip.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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